

Cloud Computing competencies questionnaire

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Objective: To measure the development of Cloud Computing competencies presented in the strengthening of the academic curriculum to meet the needs of Industry 4.0 of the higher education institutions of the Government of the State of Mexico.

Description: The numbers are the competencies, the bullets the items that measure them.

1. Uses development tools for web and mobile applications, data and client/server communications.
 - In CSS it is known as the space outside the element that separates it from the others
 - a) Margin
 - b) Padding
 - c) Border
 - d) I do not know
 - It is the most widely used software for client/server communication
 - a) HTML
 - b) Java
 - c) Apache
 - d) I do not know
 - Allows direct management of user data
 - a) Symfony
 - b) MySQL
 - c) Kotlin
 - d) I do not know
2. Apply the syntax of a language for mobile and web applications.
 - Which of the following instructions is correct?
 - a)

```
int num1 = 1;
int num2 = 2;
if (num1 < num2){
printf("The smallest number is")
printf("num1")
}
```

- b)

```
int x = 41;
x = x + 2;
if (x == 42) {
    printf("You passed!");
}
```
- c)

```
bool present = true;
if (present){
    printf("Someone attended class \n");
}
```
- d) I do not know
- This is the basic structure of an HTML5 document
 - a)

```
<html>
<head>
<title>Title</title>
</head>
<body>
</body>
</html>
```
 - b)

```
<!DOCTYPE html>
<html>
<head>
<title/>Title
</head>
<body>
</body>
</html>
```
 - c)

```
<!DOCTYPE html>
<html>
<head>
<title>Title</title>
</head>
<body>
</body>
</html>
```
 - d) I do not know
- This is the basic structure of a form
 - a)

```
<form method="">
Name: <input type="text" name="name"><br>
Email: <input type="text" name="email"><br>
<input type="submit">
</form>
```
 - b)

```
<form action="welcome.php " method="post">
Name: <input type="text" name="name"><br>
Email: <input type="text" name="email"><br>
</form>
```

- c) `<form action="welcome.php" method="post">
Name: <input type="text" name="name">

Email: <input type="text" name="email">

<input type="submit">
</form>`
 - d) I do not know
 - It is the SQL code that connects a web page to a database.
 - a) `$sql = "CREATE DATABASE myDB";
if ($conn->query($sql) === TRUE) {
 echo "Database created successfully";
} else {
 echo "Error creating database: " . $conn->error;
}`
 - b) `<?php
$servername = "localhost";
$username = "username";
$password = "password";
$conn = new mysqli($servername, $username, $password);
if ($conn->connect_error) {
 die("Connection failed: " . $conn->connect_error);
}
echo "Connected successfully";
?>`
 - c) `$conn = new mysqli($servername, $username, $password);
if ($conn->connect_error) {
 die("Connection failed: " . $conn->connect_error);
}`
 - d) I do not know
3. Develop embedded systems that enable automatic control and data transfer from a mobile device.
- Bluetooth permission settings for Android
 - a) `<manifest ... >
 <uses-permission android:name="android.permission.BLUETOOTH" />
 <uses-permission
 android:name="android.permission.BLUETOOTH_ADMIN" />
 <uses-permission
 android:name="android.permission.ACCESS_FINE_LOCATION" />
</manifest>`
 - b) `<manifest ... >
 <uses-permission android:name="android.permission.BLUETOOTH" />
 <uses-permission android:name="Android.BLUETOOTH_ADMIN" />
 <uses-permission android:name="android.permission.LOCATION" />
</manifest>`

- c) `<manifest ... >`
`<uses-permission android="android.permission.BLUETOOTH" />`
`<uses-permission`
`android:name="android.permission.BLUETOOTH_ADMIN" />`
`<permission android:name="android.permission.ACCESS_LOCATION" />`
`</manifest>`
- d) I do not know
- Allows you to register a service on the local network
 - a) `public void registerService(int port) {`
`NsdServiceInfo = new NsdServiceInfo();`
`serviceInfo.setServiceName("NsdChat");`
`serviceInfo.setServiceX("_tcp");`
`serviceInfo.setPort(port);`
`}`
 - b) `public void registerService(int port) {`
`NsdServiceInfo serviceInfo = new NsdServiceInfo();`
`serviceInfo.setServiceName("NsdChat");`
`serviceInfo.setServiceType("_nsdchat._tcp");`
`serviceInfo.setPort(port);`
`}`
 - c) `public void registerService(int port) {`
`NsdServiceInfo serviceInfo = new ServiceInfo();`
`serviceInfo.ServiceName("NsdChat");`
`serviceInfo.setServiceType("_nsdchat._tcp");`
`serviceInfo.setPort(port);`
`}`
 - d) I do not know
 - Allows autocompletion of a database from the file system
 - a) `Room.databaseBuilder(Context, AppData.class, "Sample.db")`
`.createFromFile(new File("mypath"))`
`.build();`
 - b) `Room.databaseBuilder(appContext, AppDatabase.class, "Sample.db")`
`.createFromFile(new File("mypath"))`
`.build();`
 - c) `Room.databaseBuilder(appContext, AppDatabase, Sample.db)`
`.createFromRoom(new File("mypath"))`
`.build();`
 - d) I do not know

4. Apply a troubleshooting language for mobile devices.

- It is the basic structure of a Java program
 - a) `document.getElementById("demo").style.display = "none";`
 - b) `a = 33`
`b = 200`
`if b > a:`
`print("b es mayor que a")`
 - c) `public static void main(String[] args) {`
`System.out.println("Hola mundo");`
`}`
 - d) I do not know
- This is the basic structure of a Kotlin program.
 - a) `$t = date("H");`
`if ($t < "20") {`
`echo "Have a nice day!";`
`}`
 - b) `fun main() {`
`println("Hello World!")`
`}`
 - c) `int main() {`
`cout << "Hello World!";`
`return 0;`
`}`
 - d) I do not know
- What is the result of the following code?

```
public class Main {
    public static void main(String[] args) {
        for (int i = 0; i <= 10; i = i + 2) {
            System.out.println(i);
        }
    }
}
```

 - a) 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12
 - b) 1, 3, 5, 7, 9, 11
 - c) 0, 2, 4, 6, 8, 10
 - d) I do not know
- What sequence results from the following code?

```
fun main(){
    for (i in 6 downTo 0 step 2) {
        println(i)
    }
}
```

 - a) 9, 6, 3, 0
 - b) 6, 4, 2, 0

- c) 6, 3, 0, -3
- d) I do not know

5. It uses modeling techniques for problem solving.

- Which of the following is a modeling language?
 - a) UML
 - b) Scrum
 - c) TPC/IP
 - d) C++
- Which of the following models is oriented to model processes of a system?
 - a) Class Diagram
 - b) Entity-Relationship Model
 - c) Use Case Diagram
 - d) Canvas Model
- With what can an algorithm or process be represented graphically?
 - a) Flow Diagram
 - b) Package Diagram
 - c) Object Diagram
 - d) Class Diagram

6. It uses security services, access, data, with the purpose of integrating information in the cloud in real time.

- Which of the following is NOT Cloud Computing?
 - a) AWS
 - b) Microsoft Azure
 - c) Google Cloud Platform
 - d) Safari
- What is one of the main security models implemented by Cloud services?
 - a) Centralized signing
 - b) Remote access to the cloud
 - c) Cloud Host to Host
 - d) Secure Email
- Cloud resources and workloads are exposed to a wide variety of cybersecurity threats, such as:
 - a) Data breaches
 - b) Ransomware
 - c) DDoS attacks
 - d) All of the above

7. Implements physical and virtual infrastructure for data, web and file transfer servers.
- The most basic category of cloud computing services. IT infrastructure (servers, virtual machines, storage, networks, operating systems) is rented from a cloud service provider and paid for on a per-use basis.
 - a) IaaS
 - b) PaaS
 - c) SaaS
 - d) CSS
 - What are the categories (types) of Cloud depending on the role and control exercised by user and provider?
 - a) IaaS- PaaS – SaaS
 - b) Private, public, hybrid and community
 - c) Agile, devops and container
 - d) I don't know
 - In cloud environments the update, both software and hardware, is left to the:
 - a) Service Provider
 - b) Software Developer
 - c) Customer
 - d) I don't know

Acknowledgements: The authors would like to thank PhD candidate Luis Cabrera Crot and engineers Sergio Alberto Moreno Tenorio and Juan Pablo Sanhueza for their collaboration in the design of this instrument.